

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SENTENCE STRUCTURE IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' WRITING SKILL TO PRODUCE RECOUNT TEXT ABOUT PERSONAL EXPERIENCES AT SMK AL-AMAH SINDULANG SUMEDANG

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Abstract

The aims of this study are: 1) to find out the teachers' implementation of sentence structure in developing students' writing skill, 2) to find out the effect of sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 3) to find out students' responses in producing recount text about personal experiences, 4) to find out the students' writing skill in producing recount text about personal experience. This study used qualitative method and used Classroom Action Research (CAR) as the research design. Data are collected through observation, interview, and students' work. This study is to developing students' writing skill to produce recount text about personal experiences. The population are 25 students in tenth grade of TKJ 1 Class at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang. The data result found the students' improvement in producing recount text about personal experiences. There were 84% students who achieved all the components of writing such as: content, vocabulary, grammar and mechanic. The used of implementation of sentence structure to developing students' writing skill in producing recount text about personal experiences at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang has been achieved with the data result stating that 21 students have achieved minimum completeness criterion (KKM), it means 21 students already understand how to produce recount text correctly and 4 others students have shown an increase in writing assessment where the students' score is in good category.

A. INTRODUCTION

Based on preliminary research, most high school students report that writing is the most difficult skill to master. The researchers found that there were several problems with the students' writing ability: (1) Students lack interest in writing, (2) Students lack vocabulary, (3) Students have difficulty in developing ideas (Gayatri & Gaffar, 2023). Another problem of students' writing ability at high school was added in another study such as: (1) The

students' difficulties in generating ideas, (2) The students' difficulties in organizing text, (3) The students' difficulties in constructing past sentences, (4) They are low in vocabulary mastery (Ekarista, 2018).

Another study found some factors that make students have difficulty in writing English are all the students have difficulty to understanding the structure of the text, weak in grammar, afraid of making mistakes, lack confidence, and are afraid to write for some reason. They even think they have nothing to write and they already have an idea of what to write (Barus et al., 2020).

The results of the observation, the researchers found the same problems and factors as the previous researches. Where all students in tenth grade of TKJ 1 class at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang Sumedang who have difficulty writing sentences in English, where all the students have to follow the sentence structure and the students still lack of English vocabulary that makes them unable to write. Faced with these problems, the teacher needs to use the best approaches of English Language Learning (ELL) to avoid the mistaken of students' writing (Apsari, 2017). Furthermore, the teacher must motivate students as one of the teacher roles as a motivator (Harmer, 2001). One of the ways to motivate students is to create a happy and comfortable learning atmosphere so that students can feel happy while writing (Khusnita, 2013).

To motivate students' English writing ability, the researchers provide solutions to the basic material that students must master, such as developing ideas and composing sentences according to the sentence structure in learning English. To developing ideas, researchers choose Recount text as the text type in learning writing English process. Besides, Recount text is one the form of text types (Sinthianuary, 2020), Recount text is one of genres where teach in Indonesian schools, especially in high school (Khusnita, 2013). Recount text is a text that retells everything happen in past events, usually in the order to inform and entertain which happened in the past or a text which retells experiences in the past (Anderson & Anderson, 2003 as cited in (Husna & Multazim, 2019).

In addition to making easy in develop ideas, the researchers choose recount text as a reference for students so students can understand how compose the correct sentence structure according to the level of writing ability of high school students, where the language feature of Recount text is using the simple past tense (Sugeng and Zaimah, 2007 as cited in Ningrum 2013).

From the explanation above, sentence structure may be a way to use in writing. Sentence structure is formed by the elements, such as subject, verb, object, complement and adverbial (Maniam et al., 2020). Sentence structure is a way to learn sentence in systematically which involves the structure and grammar. This approach can be used in learning to minimize the mistake. In the school, the students wrote the different text with several topics which allows students to know the supporting elements in writing (Greenbaum and Nelson 2002).

There were some previous researchers that followed these statements. The first was the study from Wati (2022) with the title is "error analysis of the students' sentence structure

in paragraph writing at the eleventh grade of SMK PGRI Pekanbaru". She used quantitative to process the data. The instrument use this study is sentence structure errors that focus on the use of nouns, adverbial, and simple past tense. The result was the total errors in using nouns in paragraph writing were 26 errors. these data, it can be seen that the total errors of sentence structure in paragraph writing made by students are 371 errors. Thus, the errors that are often made by students or the most dominant are made by class XI students of SMK PGRI Pekanbaru, namely misformation errors with a total error 303 or 81,67%. From this research, we knew that sentence structure was exactly can be used to find out the errors.

The second research, Bagus Candra Sadewa in his research entitled "The Analysis of Recount Text Written by Tenth Graders of SMAN 2 Blitar". The method used in this research is a descriptive where the researcher explained the result of research by describing the data gained. The technique used for collecting data is direct observation technique. The result of the analysis in the chapter IV, it was found that the error that have been made by most student are in orientation and events. The findings found that the tenth graders of SMA Negeri 2 Blitar have organized all of the recounts text components in their writing assignment. They were able to implement both of generic structure and language features of recounts text properly.

The differences between Wati's research (2022) and this research are 1) Wati's research used quantitative, this research uses qualitative, 2) Wati's research used test and documentation to collect the data, this research using observation, interview, and students' work. The differences between Sadewa's research (2015) and this research is in collecting data, Sadewa's research used observation and students' work, this research uses observation, interview, students' work and field notes.

Based on the statement above about the previous researches, the researchers use a personal experience as the way to teach writing skill to tenth grade of TKJ 1 class at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang Sumedang. The researchers believe that through personal experience writing, the students can more understand how to write in English systematically, can express their ideas to be better, can express their interest, and feeling. It means that the students record what happened in their life. Apart from the suitability of learning objects in high school, recount text is one of the functional writtentexts and simple short essays in the context of everyday life (Andayani & Andayani, 2013).

The aims of this study are: 1) to find out the teachers' implementation of sentence structure in developing students' writing skill, 2) to find out the effect of sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 3) to find out students' responses in producing recount text about personal experiences, 4) to find out the students' writing skill in producing recount text about personal experience.

B. METHODS

This study used descriptive qualitative approach which is more concerned with understanding situations and events from the participant's point of view, and data is

collected in the form of descriptions and tends to focus on analyzing data (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012). The researchers use Classroom Action Research (CAR) as the research design to describes both the process and results in the classroom to improve the quality of learning (Gayatri & Gaffar, 2023). The Classroom Action Research is conducted in four steps: (1) Planning, (2) Action, (3) Observing, and (4) Reflecting (Kemmis and McTaggart, 1988 as cited in Putra 2023).

To fulfill the research objectives: 1) the implementation of the sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 2) the effect of sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 3) students' response in producing a recount text about personal experiences, 4) the students' writing ability in producing a recount text about personal experiences, the researchers chose 4 instruments to collect data. Data are collected through observation, interview, and students' work.

1. Observation

The observation is carried out to collect the data during learning (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012). This study use participant observation where the researcher became a teacher and also investigated. The researcher used observation checklist to collecting the information during the research. The observation will be done in twice. In addition, on the first day of class observation, the researcher will observe the teacher in implementation of the sentence structure in developing students' writing skill. After that, the researcher will observe the students to find out students' achievement in English writing by producing personal recount text.

2. Interview

This study use structured and semi-structured interview to collect the data from the teacher and the students. Structured interview used to know the teacher in implementation of the sentence structure in developing students' writing skill, and Semi-Structured interview used to know clearly about the students' response in producing personal recount text. All the questions will ask systematically by the guideline. Interviewing is an important way for a researcher to check the accuracy of to verify or refute the impression he or she has gained through observation (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2012).

3. Students Work

This study uses Intensive Writing test from Brown (2010). The test is used for collecting the students' score in pretest, cycle I, and cycle II to find out the effect of sentence structure in developing students' writing skill and to find out students' writing skill in producing personal recount text. In the pretest researchers give a written test regarding the students' experience. In the cycle I, the researchers give a test about the story in the form of recount text, and the students have to fill in the missing past tense verbs, which aim to make the students more understand about the using of past tense in recount text. In the cycle II, the researchers give the written test about producing personal recount text, which aim to find out the students' achievement and understanding about writing English.

This research take place in SMK Al-Amah located in Jl. Parakanmuncang-Sindulang. This study is to developing students' skill to produce recount text about personal experiences. The population are 25 students in tenth grade of TKJ 1 Class at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang. the researchers choose 5 students to find out the comparison of this research results.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The analysis of the data from the observation, interview, and students' work showed that: 1) the implementation of the sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 2) the effect of sentence structure in developing students' writing skills, 3) students' response in producing a recount text about personal experiences, 4) the students' writing skill in producing a recount text about personal experiences. The researchers computed the individual students' scores and observed the students' behavior during the teaching-learning process. Classroom Action Research results are gained from the Pre-test, Cycle 1, and Cycle 2. The result will be explained as follows:

Table 1: The Result of the Student's Work

P R E - T E S T	Interval	Amount of Students	Percentages	Total Score	Mean
	81-100 Excellent	-	-	1100	44
	61-80 Good	2	8%		
	41-60 Fair	8	32%		
	21-40 Poor	15	60%		
C Y C L E I	81-100 Excellent	6	24%	1515	61
	61-80 Good	6	24%		
	41-60 Fair	4	16%		
	21-40 Poor	9	36%		
C Y C L E II	81-100 Excellent	13	52%	2036	81
	61-80 Good	12	48%		
	41-60 Fair	-	-		
	21-40 Poor	-	-		

From the table of the result of students' work showed that there was an increase in students' writing test about producing recount text. This increase came from the results of the researchers' implementation in explaining sentence structure in producing recount text such as, language features, social functions and generic structures.

Based on the table above, it is known from the overall writing skill of recount text on the pre-test. There were 2 students who got good category (8%), 8 students who got fair category (32%), and 15 students who got poor category (60%). It means that 96% of students had a low score which the minimum completeness criterion (KKM) is 75. It means that only one student who achieved the criterion by got 80 score.

On the first cycle, 6 students who got excellent category (24%), 6 students who got good category (24%), 4 students who got fair category (16%), and 9 students who got poor category (36%). From the assessment results based on the specified interval value, 24% of students got excellent categories. From the students' work, it can be seen that they still have difficulties in grammar and language features. It means after the teacher explained about social function, generic structure, and language features in the first cycle could have been more successful and will be improved in the second cycle II.

From the overall writing skill in cycle II, none of the students got the score 0-72. From the assessment results based on the specified interval value, there were 10 students who got 75-80 score, it means that the students got good category and passed the KKM. There were 13 students who got excellent category. It means that there were 21 students who passed KKM and 4 students got 73-74 score who have not passed the KKM but in good category. It means that writing a recount text about personal experience, especially in developing sentence structure using past tense in SMK Al-Amah Sindulang has been improved and students who passed the minimum completeness criterion (KKM) is 84%.

The students' score result analysis appeared that the mean score in the pre-test was 44, in first cycle was 61 and in the second cycle was 81. After students understand the material, it had a significant effect on students' writing ability, where students could achieve all the components of writing, such as content, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanic.

The other significant effect was students' achievement of scores against the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM), where the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) in SMK Al-Amah Sindulang is 75 for English Lesson. From the diagram bellow, showed students' percentages who passed the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) from Pre-Test, Cycle I and Cycle II.

From the diagram above, showed the percentages of students who passed the Minimum Completeness Criterion (KKM) from Pre-test to Cycle II. In pretest showed that only 2 students who passed the Minimum Completeness Criterion (KKM). This is caused because in the pretest students have not received an explanation about sentence structure in producing recount text such as, language features, social functions and generic structures.

In Cycle 1 showed there was a significant effect after the researcher gave the material about sentence structure in producing recount text such as, language features, social functions and generic structures, there were 40% students who passed the Minimum Completeness Criterion (KKM) or there were 10 students who got score above 75.

A comparison of the percentages of the pre-test, cycle I and cycle II, has a very significant effect where: 1) students understand more about sentence structure in producing recount text such as, language features, social functions and generic structures, 2) students are able to achieve grades in the component of writing, and 3) students are able to passed scores above the Minimum Completeness Criterion (KKM).

D. DISCUSSION

This data was taken by observation which was carried out by pre-teaching, while-teaching, and post-teaching. It is supported by Nunan (1991 as cited in Apsari, 2017) it can be concluded that the sentence structure in developing students' writing skill to produce recount text is divided into three stages; pre-teaching, while-teaching and post teaching. In addition, the researchers also divided it into three stages, namely pre-test, cycle I and cycle II.

These are the steps that have been carried out by the researchers in implementing sentence structure in developing students' writing skill to produce recount text about personal experiences at SMK AI-Amah Sindulang:

a. Pre-Teaching in Cycle I

The researchers conducted apperception to students with the aim that students could be better understand about the social functions, generic structure, and language features in the recount text. Whenever the students had difficulties in understanding the materials, the students could ask the researchers to help them to solve it.

b. While-Teaching in Cycle I

The researchers gave a test regarding personal recount text in fill-in-the-blank form with the aim that students can understand the use of past tense which is a language features in recount text. after the students collected the results of the test, the researcher assessed the results of the students' work based on the writing assessment rubric.

c. Post- Teaching in Cycle I

The researchers evaluated students' understanding by asking several students questions that can represent the class's understanding of today's learning material.

In cycle I the researchers conducted a pre-test to find out students' writing skill before writing a personal recount text based on social function, generic structure and language features. This is in line of opinion by Gayatri and Gaffar (2023) the researcher conducted a pre-test to identify the students' ability to write recount text. Furthermore, here are the steps in cycle 2

a. Pre-Teaching in Cycle II

The researchers conducted apperception to students with the aim that students could be better understand about the social functions, language features, and generic structure in producing the recount text.

b. While-Teaching in Cycle II

The researchers gave a written test to students to writing a recount text about personal experiences by paying attention to the social function, structure and language features of a recount text. It aims to find out the increase in students' writing skills in making personal recount text after the researchers taught recount text material and sentence structure.

c. Post-Teaching in Cycle II

The researchers evaluated students' writing skills in producing recount text about personal experiences by assessed the results of the students' work based on the writing assessment rubric.

After the researchers conducted interviews, it was found that the aim of learning using recount text about personal experiences in tenth grade of TKJ 1 class at SMK AI-Amah Sindulang, was for students to be able to write English according to the sentence

structure. Where recount text is also included in the English learning object. To prepare for teaching the researchers made a Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) and prepares learning tools and media. To measure the improvement in students' writing skills, the researchers gave several various tests, including fill in the blank and a writing test (essay) about recount text. After that the researchers analyzed the results of the student test by giving score according to the writing assessment rubric with the Minimum Mastery Criteria (KKM) is 75.

Based on the results that the researchers found on this research, that sentence structure in developing students writing skills have a good contribution effect to the students' skill in writing recount text. From the comparison of student's writing scores, the researchers found that the significant difference between the result of students Pre-test, Cycle I and Cycle II, from the chart above in result, showed that the effect of sentence structure in developing Students' writing skills to produce recount text about Personal Experiences at SMK Al-Amah Sindulang greatly improved and 84% students passed the minimum completeness criterion (KKM) which there were 21 students who got the score above 75.

The contribution of the sentence structure in developing students' skill to produce recount text about personal experience is in line with Sadewa's (2015) study, students were able to implement both of generic structure, language features and grammar in making recounts text. It means Sadewa's research strengthens this study that sentence structure can give good contribution on developing students writing skills in producing recount text.

In line with the effect of the students' ability in writing recount text, this result is corroborated by Ningrum, et. Al (2013), the researchers found that students already understood how to write recount text paragraph with the implementation of sentence structure. In post-test the percentage of students who got the highest score was 84%. There were 7 students (28%) who got the highest, and there was only 1 student (4%) who got the lowest. In short, students' score was increased from the pre-test to the post-test. Ningrum's research confirmed that using sentence structure to developing students writing skills in producing recount text can give a good contribution.

Such as Sukma' (2015) study results that support the results of this study, showed that implementation of sentence structure in developing students writing skills to produce recount text has a good contribution on organization sentence, students' grammar ability, students writing skills and Content of the recount text. The results of Sukma's research on organization sentence is 2 students (6,67%) were at very good category, 12 students (40%) were at good category, 11 students (36,6%) were at fair category, and 5 students (16,67%) were at poor category and There was no students were at very poor category. It means that almost students write organization by using connective word like first, after that, and finally in the event with almost true connective. While the results of Sukma's research on students' grammar ability is 1 student (3,33%) were very good because the student could write grammar correctly by using simple past and word order. And 3 students (10%) were good category because the students write grammatical and word order not accuracy but not change the meaning; 11 students (36,7%) were fair category; 12 students (40%) were poor category, and 3 students (10%) were very poor

category. It means that most students had problem in grammar. It caused by the lack of ability in grammar. The results of Sukma's research on students writing skills is 1 student (3,33%) was very good category, 11 students (36,7%) were good category, 16 students (53,3%) were fair category, 2 students (6,67%) were poor category and There was no students were very poor category. It means that the students' writing skill in producing recount text on Sukma's research was on fair category. And the results of the content of the recount text of Sukma's research is It means that almost students write organization by using connective word like first, after that, and finally in the event with almost true connective. Sukma's research supports that the results of using the correct sentence structure can provide a good contribution to improving students' writing skills in creating recount text

Here the researchers considered that by using sentence structure in developing students writing skills to produce recount text can help in reflecting on their own experience and learning process and using meaningful criteria to determine learning achievement and self-empowerment. According to Greenbaum & Nelson (2002) sentence structure is a way to learn sentence in systematically which involves the structure and grammar. This approach can be used in learning to minimize the mistake. in the school, the students wrote the differentiate text with several topics which allows students to know the supporting elements in writing.

In collecting students' responses in producing recount text about personal experiences, the researchers used observation and semi-structured interview. The observation checklist was the researchers' choice to see the results students' responses during the learning process in producing recount text about personal experiences. The responses can be seen by student's expression, comment or enthusiasm, difficulty degrees, even by how students listening to the researcher explanation (Riyana & Susilani, 2007 as cited in Muhlisin 2018). Based on the result of observation in cycle 2 it showed that students' responses in producing recount text about their own experiences was quite responsive, where some students begin to respond to what the researchers asked or ordered in the learning process in producing recount text about personal experiences. This was also because students already understand enough about the recount text material that has been explained by researchers in cycle 1, so that some students gave positive responses when the researchers gave an explanation of the recount text material. It is relevant to Pertiwi & Kareviati (2021) that the student's responses can be positive or negative. The students with positive responses will tend to like and pay attention to the learning process, while the students with negative responses will tend to dislike and ignore it. The responses of the students may affect the student's motivation to learn. Hence, motivation also can affect a student's writing.

In the interview section, the researchers used semi-structured interview to five students as the sample which consisted of 4 questions. Semi-structured interview allows depth to be achieved by providing the opportunity on the part of the interviewer to probe and expand the interviewee's responses (Rubin & Rubin, 2005 as cited in Rismayanti et al., 2022). The interview was conducted to gain the students' responses regarding their

knowledge to producing recount text is based on writing aspect such as: content, vocabulary, grammar and mechanic. According to Brown (2010) there were five aspects in writing process, such as organization, content, vocabulary, grammar and mechanic. Based on the result in interview, it showed that three students gave good responses regarding their knowledge of writing aspects in producing personal recount text. While the other students felt that they did not really understand what aspects of writing they had to apply in producing recount text about personal experiences.

Based on the explanation above it showed that students' responses in producing recount text about personal experiences was good, which can be seen from the result during the observation of the learning process in producing personal recount text that some students were seen doing the assignments given by the researchers and some of them asked questions about the recount text material. And the result of the interviews also showed good responses from students regarding their knowledge the aspects of writing in producing recount text about personal experiences.

Based on the observation result of students' responses in producing recount text about personal experiences was quite good, it caused in students' writing skill has been increasing and the students more understand how to write systematically. The data of the students' writing skill were obtained by scoring students' writing skill in producing a Recount text about students' personal experiences and analyzing that measured based on some components, such as content, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanic. These four components become one of the difficulties faced by students in writing, especially in writing English ability (Citra & Apsari, 2020). To measure, this study used of scoring writing assessment rubric adapted by Brown (2007). From Husna's result study of the analysis found the most difficulties in the students' writing recount text are grammatical error, content in composing writing, mechanic aspect and in the generic structure of recount text (Husna & Multazim, 2019).

From the scoring writing assessment rubric result in cycle I, the researchers found that the difficulties faced by the students were from grammar and mechanic, where there were 44% students who got fair-poor score in grammar and 26% students who got fair-poor score in mechanic. But from the study researched by Kemala (2017) It occurs about 32% on grammar. After that, Punctuation problems occur about 24% (2017) (Kemala Sari et al., 2017). From the comparison of these result study, grammar is one component that students find difficult. The students' mother tongue was still influenced the way of students' writing and intralingual transfer. It related with the students' knowledge in using correct grammar. Students had lack of grammar knowledge that made them did many errors in their writing (Yulianawati, 2018).

To analyzing students' writing skill in producing a recount text about students' personal experiences have been improvement or not, the researchers analyzed it from the scoring writing assessment rubric result in cycle I and cycle II. From the study researched by Yusnita et al (2013) found that there was an improvement in students' writing skill in the process of cycle I and cycle II. This is because the researchers focused more on implementing the use of picture series so that students better understand how to make

recount text. Same with this study, where the researchers were giving more explanation about sentence structure in producing recount text such as, language features, social functions and generic structures.

After having the results of this research, the findings of this research can be seen in the process of cycle 1 and cycle 2. From the result of cycle 1, it was mentioned that in this cycle the students' achievement of recount text writing was 40% students had achieved, so it means 60% students not achieved. It because of some students still difficult to understand the way to produce the recount text based on features, social functions and generic structures. These happened because students still need more time to understand how to produce the recount text correctly (Yusnita et al., 2013).

In cycle II, the researchers found the students' improvement in producing recount text about personal experiences. Based on scoring writing assessment rubric adapted by Brown (2007), there was 84% students who achieved all the components of writing from good to excellent category. It means 21 students already understand how to produce personal recount text, correctly. many students can express their idea easily and develop their ideas in writing easier after learning how produce recount text (Apsari, 2017). From the result above, showed that this study in implementation of sentence structure in developing students' writing skill to produce recount text about personal experiences in SMK Al-Amah Sindulang was completely success, students' writing achievement could pass the minimum completeness criterion (KKM) and the students achieved all the good to excellent category in writing assessment rubric as a measure of student achievement.

E. CONCLUSION

In this study, researchers have conducted research on the used of recount text about personal experiences to developing students' writing skill bring many benefits for students, especially after the researchers gave more attention in explaining about the implementation of sentence structure, language features, social function, and generic structure in recount text in cycle I and cycle II. Based on the data result, it showed students' improvement in writing skill. The used Recount Text about personal experiences in learning writing recount text also help the students achieve more in writing assessment and help the students to passed the minimum completeness criterion (KKM). Furthermore, students' motivation in writing especially in writing recount text about personal experiences has increased enough, where students more enjoy and many students respond quite well during the learning process.

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